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THE VALUE OF OPEN-ENDED PROBLEMS IN DESIGN PEDAGOGY

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ABSTRACT

In a traditional design studio, students are assigned framed problems with a stated solution at the start of a project. Students approach the problem knowing the outcome will be a brochure, logo, website, etc. However, as the student enters the design field, they will not solve prescribed problems, but approach problems from a variety of angles. To move away from artifact based problem solving, this paper presents a case study using open-ended problems. Open-ended problems focus on research, strategy and process. No deliverables were stated, rather questions were asked to enhance student exploration. Students became self-learners and self-starters, using critical thinking skills to evaluate possible solutions. Posing an open-ended problem resulted in research-driven diverse solutions.

Keywords: design pedagogy, open-ended problems, design research

INTRODUCTION

A student's design education begins with learning the fundamentals of form. They study composition, hierarchy, design theory, type and image relationships. The problems students face are often void of content, focusing on formal aspects. As the student advances they transition into conceptual problem-solving projects and content is introduced. Class assignments range from designing a book, poster, or brochure to interface design, branding and packaging. What remains a constant is the artifact they are designing is almost always given to them at the onset of a project. Here is the problem; here is what the solution will be.

This paper presents a case study involving junior-level visual communication design students at Kent State University in The School of Visual Communication Design (VCD). To shift students attention away from artifact based problem solving, they were given an open-ended problem. Open-ended problems focus on research, strategy and process. No deliverables were stated, rather questions were asked to enhance student exploration. Students became self-learners and self-starters, using critical thinking skills to evaluate possible solutions.

DESIGN AS PROCESS

The word design is both a noun and a verb (Lawson, 3). Too often, more emphasis is placed on design as a noun, referring to the artifact a designer creates. The general public's view of a designer as a maker of things further highlights the end product and not the process. Frank Chimero, a designer and educator, states, "If it's wrong for a client to believe the value of design is in the nouns, it's also incorrect to educate a designer around nouns. Curriculums shouldn't be focused towards teaching software or creating specific artifacts." As design educators, we must shift our methods of education away from artifact-based problem solving, putting the value in the process.

The process should involve careful analysis, critical inquiry and strategic thinking. In her paper titled, *The Design Studio: A Site for Critical Inquiry*, Malika Bose argues that the design process should involve problem structuring and problem solving. "The solution depends largely on how the problem is

defined, since often it is the act of problem definition that sets the limits of the problem space” (131). As educators, providing the solution to the problem sets limits on the outcomes. We used an open-ended problem to structure this project.

OPEN-ENDED PROBLEMS

An open-ended problem has multiple solutions and correct answers. The design field is evolving and many designers currently face difficult open-ended problems. Clients no longer need just a logo, brochure or website. Rather, designers will be solving complex problems of building awareness, increasing enrollment or expanding financial support. Due to these contemporary demands of the profession, designers need to adapt to solving problems without prescribed solutions.

VCD students at Kent State University take a design research course during their sophomore year. Learning research methods used in the professional practice of design, they are exposed to strategies, tactics and frameworks used in the creation of design artifacts. Traditional design problems are based around the creation of a single artifact. The problem is this method often follows a linear path; the end result never changes nor involves research-driven decisions as to what this artifact could be. If a student knows they have to design a brochure, that is exactly what they do. Tactics such as ethnography, observation, interviews and user testing go unused. In contrast, the research-driven design process depends on assessment throughout a project. This allows the designer to reconsider assumptions they made based on their primary research. Using their collected data, a designer may make changes throughout the course of a project as their research dictates new directions. This process of analysis creates a culture of consultation. As a result, research driven-designers engage in long-term relationships with their clients as strategic partners (Visocky, 67).

Prior to teaching the junior-level design course, my colleagues and I started with the hypothesis, using open-ended problems will cultivate a research-driven design environment. In addition, using open-ended problems would allow for diverse and unique

outcomes to the problem. When a solution is not given at the beginning of a project, the student becomes the one identifying the appropriate outcome. Our goal was for them to use their research to identify problems, analyze and evaluate results, generating unique solutions. In the book titled *Design Studio Pedagogy: Horizons for the future*, Ashraf Salama and Nicholas Wilkinson argue that research and critical inquiry must be the backbone of design pedagogy (126).

THE ASSIGNMENT: VISUAL NARRATIVE & MAPPING

The students were assigned a visual narrative and mapping project. They documented an event, journey or experience through photography and typography in an exploratory visual narrative. Using narrative and informational elements, they communicated their experience to an audience. The learning objectives were:

- Learning to represent narrative elements
- Learning how to use information design to aid in communication
- Learning concept development, design research and execution
- Learning to design for object interaction and to entice playful exploration
- Learning methods in visual representation and documentation

ASKING QUESTIONS TO ENHANCE EXPLORATION

As the problem was open-ended, no deliverables were stated. Rather, the following open-ended questions were asked throughout the assignment,

- How can you make the experience meaningful?
- How can the audience see through your perspective?
- Can you make the familiar strange, new or some how different?

Questioning is an important step in any design process and designing should be question intensive. (Eris, 1) Why not start with questions at the beginning of a class project, just as we would do with a new client? We ask clients questions regarding

their needs, but we provide our students with the solutions. Ozgur Eris, author of *Effective Inquiry for Innovative Engineering Design*, says “Questioning is an important step, but can often be overlooked. Questioning provides many divergent paths that bring you to the best idea, rather than providing a straight and narrow path ahead.” When we provide students with the solution, we send them down the straight and narrow path. The question prompts were continually referred to throughout the assignment as the students progressed. This basic set of questions raised new questions and led students down a path of discovery.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Past project student ‘research’ usually consisted of a page of inspiration examples they pulled of the Internet. There was a disconnect between what the students learned in their research class and how they applied it within their studio classes. This was in part because solution-driven class projects did not allow for them to adequately apply the knowledge. Through class discussion we encouraged them to use methods they learned from their design research course. Beginning with primary research, they documented a trip or experience through journaling, photographs and videos. Some students used surveys and interviews as they further researched their topic. Students conducted secondary research as they analyzed the data they collected and pursued supplemental sources of information. Storyboards were used to visually articulate their experience. As they evaluated their findings students began creating prototypes of what the solutions to their projects would be. A prototype is a visual that suggests the functionality and look of the final product. This can be a paper prototype, a sketch or a digital rendering (Fogg, 205).

RESULTS

Using an open-ended problem was successful in producing diverse solutions and fostering a research-driven environment. One student visited the historic West Side Market in Cleveland. Feeling lost, confused and over-whelmed by the 100+ vendors, her experience led her to create a mapping system. Inspired by her curiosity with organic food, another

student cooked an organic meal. Based on her experience, along with interviews and surveys, she prepared a kit with everything one would need to prepare an organic meal including recipes, a shopping bag, produce facts and information. One student’s project involved shopping for a suit. He used observational research as he watched people shopping for suits, conducted interviews with a tailor and experienced first hand the process of getting a suit fitted. (Figure 1)

IN MY EXPERIENCE

1. Get measured
2. Choose a suit or two...or three, or four
3. Try on jackets, make marks for tailoring
4. Try on pants, make marks

Figure 1. Research conducted for class project.

After researching advertisements for suits, often involving men in numerous fashion poses, very sleek, slick, he knew he wanted to take a different approach with his designs. The end result was an educational book about suits targeted towards college students as they enter the job market. The book provides detailed, important information in an approachable, humorous way. (Figure 2)

Figure 2. Final class project.

Visiting a local animal shelter, one student conducted observations and interviews with staff and people looking to adopt. This research propelled him to create a kit for people new to the adoption process. After his experience going to a neighborhood in Cleveland, one student created a social networking forum where you plan an outing. (Figure 3) The site allowed users to create various 'sparks' based on what one was in the mood for, a lunch date, an evening on the town, etc. The student

Figure 3. Sparkify, student project.

is planning on continuing with this project beginning site development and user testing. Lastly, one student experienced dumpster diving with her fellow peers. (Figure 4) This project took the form of a trash can where each level reveals additional information: a narrative, an informational graphic on wasted in the United States and tips if you want to experience this yourself.

Figure 4. Foraging with Freegans, student project.

Student learning was assessed through anonymous surveys, peer assessment and meetings with the professor. Students were asked if they preferred: a.) *framed projects that state what the final artifact (poster, website, etc) would be;* or b.) *unframed/open-ended projects that let my research dictate the final artifacts.* Survey evidence supported the positive feedback received from the students in the classroom as 75% preferred option b, unframed/open-ended projects. The survey was also used to assess the effectiveness of using question prompts to help guide student exploration. The response was overwhelmingly in favor of question prompts with 94% of students stated they were helpful. (Figure 5)

Student feedback was also assessed through written reflections at the completion of the project. While many stated it was “daunting to work with little parameters”, they felt satisfied with their overall piece. Numerous students commented that the most difficult part was simply starting the project, due to fear of not knowing what the final result would be. Once they focused on a direction, fears subsided.

CONCLUSION

This course was designed to foster self-initiative among the students. As students transitioned from a teacher-centered environment to a more self-directed course they experienced confusion and frustration. This was their first experience working on an entirely open-ended problem; there were many obstacles to overcome. For some, the jump was too drastic. With prior problems always providing the solutions, this project was like tossing them into the water without a life jacket. In looking at ways to ease this transition, curriculum changes need to occur to slowly introduce students to open-ended problems and bring more research into the classroom.

Despite the initial discomfort students felt, there was a sense of accomplishment with the completion of the project. When asked if the open-ended problem was challenging and frustrating or challenging yet rewarding, 90% picked the latter. Even though the project had its difficult moments, the students embraced the opportunity to thrive in

this new learning environment. Not only do open-ended problems improve student research skills, in this discovery-led process of design students become active learners. Active learning involves students discovering, processing and applying information verses the alternative of listening to a lecture or reading a textbook. Open-ended problems encourage student initiative and ownership of the process. They provide the students freedom to entertain a variety of possible solutions while enhancing their design research skills.

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Figure 5. Survey results. Given to two different class periods, totaling 32 students.